

Project¹ Number: 101030965

Project Acronym: PHERADOA

Project title: Pharmacological therapy to curtail visual loss in ADOA mouse model

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

¹ The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

1. Data Summary

The proposal of the PHERADOA project is to develop a pharmacological therapy to reduce the visual loss of the ADOA mouse. The DMP of PHERADOA will describe how the data obtained will be processed, analysed, and stored with the aim of making it accessible and reusable according to H2020 FAIR Data Management principles. In addition, the analysis of the data collected helps policy makers in the creation of public policies in favour of patients affected by the disease.

1.1. Types of the data generated:

Data will be numeric in Excel, CSV or any other text formats for research and data-analysis purposes.

- Molecular data on animal mice genome.
- Measurements in biological tissues in animal mice eyes.
- Chemical data (particles polymer-based characterization).
- Behaviour data in animal mouse model.

1.2. Formats of data generated:

- Documents/Reports/Publications: PDF, txt, doc/docx
- Spreadsheets: xls/xlsx
- Databases: cvs
- Pictures: jpg, png, TIF
- Video: avi, flv, mov, mp4, wmv

1.3. Re-use any existing data

Existing data will not be used for other research projects.

1.4. Origin of data:

The data will be collected locally at Department of Biology and department of pharmaceutical sciences, both at University of Padova.

1.5. Expected size of the data

To be evaluated during the project.

1.6. Data utility

- European Commission services and European Agencies.
- EU National Bodies.
- Scientific community.
- Policy makers.
- ADOA patients.

2. FAIR data

2. 1. Making data findable and openly accessible, including provisions for metadata

This project will follow the Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020 and the data generated will be collected in scientific publications (peer-reviewed articles, conference, workshops, patents), dissemination and outreach material (presentations and posters at conferences, flyers, videos, press releases, etc.), deliverables and reports.

All the experiments in laboratory will be documented in protocols in laboratory notebooks to ensure the reproducibility of the data. All the electronic data will be stored in folder structures to group files using clear and descriptive names. Files will be uniquely named and versioned: dataset name, project name, and date.

Making data findable is realized by choosing Zenodo platform for storing and publishing as well as assigning the relevant metadata. All public datasets, scientific publications and deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo and made openly available, free of charge. Publications and underlying data sets will be linked through use of persistent identifiers (DOI versioning).

2.2. Making data interoperable

The project will collect and document the data in a standardized way (using formats: ASCII, txt, csv, xml, tiff, cdx, obj, etc.) to ensure that datasets can be correctly understood, interpreted, and re-used.

2.3. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The data will be available through the website that will be created for science communication and the intent is that the Research Data generated be reusable even after the end of the project, if allowed, and supported by the project resources and the necessary infrastructure. Creative Common copyright Licenses will be used for all data to be preserved.

3. Allocation of resources

Article Processing Charges (APCs) will be covered by the project funds to allow free-access to scientific articles upon publication. All public data, documents and deliverables will be archived and preserved on Zenodo and will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. The prof. Luca Scorrano, from the department of biology will be responsible for data management in your project.

4. Data security

The results of experiments will be storage on network and local drives provided by the institution, which are backed-up on external hard drives. The data will also be available in the form of project reports and open access publications.

5. Ethical aspects

The project will use mice samples; therefore, we will obtain all ethical requirements that complies with applicable international (EU Directive 2010/63) and national law (D.L. 26/2014). We will not proceed with any research containing ethical implications before obtaining the opinions/approvals from ethics committees for activities raising ethical issues required under national and/or European law.

6. Other issues

NO other issue

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	24.05.2022	▪ Initial version
1.1	28.06.2022	▪ Reviewed version 1
1.2	09.08.2022	▪ Reviewed version 2